

SITE GPR	YEAR 2010	AREA B	SECTOR	ELEVATION Min: 63.323 Max: 63.5742	STRATIGRAPHICAL UNIT 1163 <input type="checkbox"/> Natural <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Anthropic	 Gabi Project
In cross-section? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No			In elevation drawing? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No		Photos: <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No #: D601-607	Photo Model: <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No #:
DEFINITION Bubble Wall continuation of 1135					Covered by SU: 1016	Fills SU: 1171
HOW IS LAYER DISTINGUISHED? <input type="checkbox"/> Color <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Composition <input type="checkbox"/> Compaction			FORMATION PROCESS <input type="checkbox"/> Accumulation <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Construction <input type="checkbox"/> Cutting <input type="checkbox"/> Erosion <input type="checkbox"/> Collapse <input type="checkbox"/> Intentional deposition			
INCLUSIONS For each inclusion specify frequency: (f)requent, (m)edium, (r)are					SOIL/MATRIX	
Anthropic			Geological		Organic	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Pottery <input type="checkbox"/> Nails <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Tiles <input type="checkbox"/> Marble <input type="checkbox"/> Amphorae <input type="checkbox"/> Quarried debris <input type="checkbox"/> Dolia <input type="checkbox"/> Slag <input type="checkbox"/> Brick <input type="checkbox"/> Mosaic tile(s) <input type="checkbox"/> Basalt slabs <input type="checkbox"/> Mortar <input type="checkbox"/> Opus signinum <input type="checkbox"/> Coins <input type="checkbox"/> Painted plaster <input type="checkbox"/> Metal (specify) <input type="checkbox"/> Burnt Adobe <input type="checkbox"/> Collapse debris <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify) <input type="checkbox"/> Glass			<input type="checkbox"/> Tufo (specify) <input type="checkbox"/> Travertine <input type="checkbox"/> Other Limestone <input type="checkbox"/> Basalt <input type="checkbox"/> Clay <input type="checkbox"/> Sand <input type="checkbox"/> Silt <input type="checkbox"/> Pebbles (range) <input type="checkbox"/> Gravel (range)		<input type="checkbox"/> Charcoal <input type="checkbox"/> Ash <input type="checkbox"/> Animal bones <input type="checkbox"/> Human bones <input type="checkbox"/> Animal teeth <input type="checkbox"/> Human teeth <input type="checkbox"/> Shells <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)	
					clay ___% silt ___% sand ___%	
					<input type="checkbox"/> Granular <input type="checkbox"/> Layered <input type="checkbox"/> Cohesive	
					Compaction	
					<input type="checkbox"/> Hard	
					<input type="checkbox"/> Compact	
					<input type="checkbox"/> Friable	
					<input type="checkbox"/> Loose	
					<input type="checkbox"/> Soft	
					Color	
					<input type="checkbox"/> Black <input type="checkbox"/> Brown	
					<input type="checkbox"/> Gray <input type="checkbox"/> Light Brown	
					<input type="checkbox"/> Light Gray <input type="checkbox"/> White	
					<input type="checkbox"/> Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Red	
					<input type="checkbox"/> Light Yellow	
					<input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)	
UNIT LIMITS (also indicate on overlay)						
Northern Limit <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit Depth: <input type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original						
Southern Limit <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit						
Western Limit <input type="checkbox"/> Original <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit out by 1152						
Eastern Limit <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit						
STRATIGRAPHICAL SEQUENCE						
Is equal to: 1135			Is bound to (only for masonry):			
Is abutted by:			Abuts: Tub wall feature 1186			
Is covered by: 1016			Covers:			
Is cut by: 1152			Cuts:			
Is filled by:			Fills: 1171			
OBSERVATIONS 1163 is a continuation of the rubble wall, 1135. It seems that so far the wall ends as it meets with a Tufo wall feature, located east of 1163. As 1163 approaches this Tufo wall, its height and also density of compositional rubble decreases.						
DESCRIPTION						
Position within sector: Located on the southern half of the sector, immediately east of 1135 and 1152.						
Shape: Overall shape is linear.						
For layers complete this section:						
Surface (slope direction; visible inclusions):						
Observations about inclusions (Clusters? Deposition slope):						
Observations about thickness (Increases? Decreases?):						
Nature of the interface with layer below: <input type="checkbox"/> sharp <input type="checkbox"/> diffuse <input type="checkbox"/> commigled <input type="checkbox"/> other (specify)						
For cuts complete this section:			Sketch for layers and/or cuts (indicate North):			
Cut edges: <input type="checkbox"/> rounded <input type="checkbox"/> straight						
Cut sides <input type="checkbox"/> straight <input type="checkbox"/> concave <input type="checkbox"/> convex <input type="checkbox"/> sloping						
Cut bottom: <input type="checkbox"/> flat <input type="checkbox"/> concave <input type="checkbox"/> irregular						
How is cut top edge? <input type="checkbox"/> sharp <input type="checkbox"/> rounded						
How is cut bottom edge? <input type="checkbox"/> sharp <input type="checkbox"/> rounded						
Observations:						

For structural remains complete this section

Alignment:

Building Technique: Adobe/Mud-brick Ashlar (blocks) Irregular (unworked) stone Concrete Other (specify)

Binding Agent: None Clay Mortar (if so, specify composition, color, compaction)

Concrete inclusions:

Material Tufo Basalt Travertine Tiles Other (specify)
 Size Small (range) 7cm Medium (range) 10cm Large (range) 21cm Representative size: e.g. 2 x 1 x 2 cm

Wall Facing:

Opus quadratum Opus incertum Opus reticulatum Petit appareil Opus testaceum Opus mixtum Opus vittatum Other (specify)

Complete this section for foundations Faced foundation Wooden shuttering No shuttering

→ Republican Opus Mixtum

Floor/revetment type N/A

Floor type: Beaten Earth Opus signinum Opus scutulatum Opus Sectile Mosaic Opus spicatum Other (specify)

Wall finishing Stucco Opus signinum Plaster Painted Plaster Other (specify)

Approx. length, width, height of structural remains:

293cm length height = 11 → 2cm
63cm width

Description:

Rubble wall feature is oriented West to east and is a continuation of 1135. As one follows the wall feature east there is a slight decline. Also the frequency of wall material decreases on the eastern portion of the wall.

Sketch (if applicable, indicate North)

INTERPRETATION

1163 is a continuation of the rubble wall feature 1135. Its association with the tufo wall feature is still undetermined, however it was observed that 1163 ends at this tufo wall. Currently, it seems that 1163 in conjunction with 1135 predates the burial of lordy gaga, 1155. This observation was reached after comparing the relationship between 1152 and 1155. Also the positioning of the burial 1155 indicates that the persons who dug the grave were aware of the rubble wall feature. Finally the depth of 1155 is similar to that of 1163 and if the Rubble wall once stood fully exposed - it seems unlikely that the burial would be placed above ground.

- 1170 - Cut for Rubble wall 1135
- 1171 = Cut for Rubble wall 1163
- 1172 - Cut for Rubble wall 1162
- 1152 = from 1155 = lordy gaga

SOIL SAMPLING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

NON SOIL SAMPLES: Yes No

If yes, specify (e.g. charcoal, mortar etc.):

Size:

SIEVING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

STRATIGRAPHICAL RELIABILITY

Good Fair Poor

Filled-out by Demaine Francis on 13-7-10

Revised by CHM on 19.7.2011

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Entered by _____ on _____